

dioxane molecules may be proposed for these complexes.

Magnetic susceptibilities of UCl_5 complexes have been studied by various workers¹⁻⁵. Magnetic susceptibilities of UCl_5 , 2-methyleneanthrone, UCl_5 , 2-benzalanthrone and UCl_5 , 2-dioxane have been measured at room temperature only giving μ_{eff} values of 1.81, 1.75, and 1.71 B.M., respectively. These values are very close to the spin value only.

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Preparation of 4'-Amino-3-carboxy-6-methoxydiphenyl Sulphide and its Derivatives

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3-Mercaptoanisic acid has been obtained by the reduction of 3-chlorosulphonylanisic acid¹ by Gattermann's method² or by hydrolysis of the xanthate derivative of 3-aminoanisic acid³. We have now obtained this compound in 81% yield by reducing 3-chlorosulphonylanisic acid with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. It was characterised through some new derivatives, viz. disulphide, ethyl thioether and thioglycollic acid. We also record here the preparation of hitherto unreported 3-carboxy-6-methoxy-4'-nitrodiphenyl sulphide by condensation of the mercaptan with 4-chloronitrobenzene and its reduction product 4'-amino-3-carboxy-6-methoxydiphenyl sulphide.

*Satisfactory elemental analysis have been obtained for all the compounds reported.

Experimental*

3-Mercaptoanisic acid: To a warm acetic acid solution (100 ml) of 3-chlorosulphonylanisic acid (0.02 mole), prepared in 68% yield by the chlorosulphonation of anisic acid⁴, was gradually added with swirling $SnCl_2$ (0.05 mole) dissolved in conc. HCl (12 ml). The mixture was refluxed for an hour, cooled and poured into cold water (600 ml) containing conc. HCl (25ml). The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetone to give pale yellow crystals. m.p. 236° (lit. 220°³ and 317°¹). Yield 81.5%, (Found: C, 52.03; H, 4.20; S, 17.3 Calcd. for $C_8H_8O_3S$; C, 52.18; H, 4.35; S, 17.39%).

6,6'-Dimethoxy-3, 3'-dicarboxydiphenyl disulphide: The mercaptan on oxidation with Na_2CO_3 and I_2 solution gave the disulphide, $C_{16}H_{14}O_8S_2$, m.p. 339° in 67.5% yield.

Ethyl-3-carboxy-6-methoxyphenyl sulphide: Sodium (2 g) was gradually added to refluxing dry ethanol (40 ml) followed successively by 3-mercaptoanisic acid (0.01 mole) and ethyl bromide (5 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr, water (10 ml) added and the excess ethyl bromide and ethanol distilled off. The aqueous solution on acidification gave the desired compound, $C_{10}H_{12}O_3S$, crystallised from ethanol (30%) in white flakes m.p. 139° in 73% yield.

3-Carboxy-6-methoxyphenylthioglycollic acid: 3-Mercaptoanisic acid (0.01 mole) was condensed with chloroacetic acid (0.01 mole) using alc. KOH⁵. The product $C_{10}H_{10}O_5S$, m.p. 214° (50% ethanol) was obtained in 68% yield.

3-Carboxy-6-methoxy-4'-nitrodiphenyl sulphide: 3-Mercaptoanisic acid (0.01 mole) was condensed⁶ with 4-chloronitrobenzene (0.01 mole) using alc. KOH. Yield 58.7%, m.p. 210° (ethanol). It analysed for $C_{14}H_{11}O_5NS$.

4'-Amino-3-carboxy-6-methoxydiphenyl sulphide: Best yield of the amine was obtained when the above nitro derivative was reduced in ethanol with Sn and HCl. After the reduction, the pH was raised to 6-7 with NaOH and the precipitated amine was extracted with ethanol. It was dissolved in 20% $NaHCO_3$, filtered and acidified with AcOH. It was crystallised from ethanol to give pale brown crystals, m.p. 250°, in 56% yield. (Found: C, 60.91; H, 5.0; N, 5.09; S, 11.91. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{15}O_3NS$: C, 61.09; H, 4.73; N, 5.1; S, 11.63%).

The amine was characterised through its acetyl ($C_{18}H_{15}O_4NS$, m.p. 287°), tosyl ($C_{21}H_{19}O_5NS_2$, m.p. 226°), brosyl ($C_{20}H_{16}O_5BrNS_2$, m.p. 232°), N-substituted phthalimide ($C_{22}H_{15}O_5NS$, m.p. 241°), N-substituted-3-nitrophthalimide ($C_{22}H_{14}O_7N_2S$, m.p. 274°) and N-substituted succinimide ($C_{18}H_{15}O_5NS$, m.p. 216°) derivatives.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Manganese Employing N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-benzylbenzamide Hydrochloride (HPBBAH)

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FASCINATED by the analytical potentialities of N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidines¹⁻⁵, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise and investigate the complexing properties of a hydroxyamidine analogue in which a methylene group is introduced in between azomethine nitrogen atom and the N'-aryl ring. Thus, in the course of the study, it is found that N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-benzylbenzamide hydrochloride, abbreviated as HPBBAH, reacts with many transition metal ions in a manner analogous to other hydroxyamidines. However, a distinct change in its behaviour with manganese(II) has been noted. Whereas the hydroxyamidines reported earlier^{6,7}, develop a yellow-green colour with manganese(II) in ammoniacal medium⁸, HPBBAH gives an instantaneous and sensitive blue colour in ethanol. Based on this colour reaction, a simple rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of microgram quantities of manganese.

Experimental

Preparation and the properties of the reagent: HPBBAH was prepared by coupling equimolar ethereal solutions of N-benzylbenzimidoyl chloride and N-phenylhydroxylamine at 0-5° following the general method for the synthesis of hydroxyamidines⁶. The resulting white solid after washing with ether was recrystallised from absolute alcohol containing a few drops of HCl. White shining crystals of the compound melted at 195° (C₂₀H₁₉N₂OCl. requires: C, 70.93; H, 5.61; N, 8.27%, found: C, 70.85; H, 5.76; N, 8.20%)

IR Spectra (nujol-hexachlorobutadiene): ν_{\max} , 2450

(=N-H); 1620 (-C=NH); 935 (N-O) cm⁻¹.

UV Spectra: $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$, 213 nm (ϵ , 22500); 300 nm (ϵ , 7050).

A 2% solution of the reagent in ethanol was employed for the development of the colour.

A stock solution of manganese(II) was prepared by dissolving MnCl₂·2H₂O in double distilled water containing few drops of HCl. The solution was standardised complexometrically^{9,10}. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade chemicals.

Infrared and ultraviolet spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 221 and Carl-Zeiss 'Specord' (UV/VIS) spectrophotometers respectively. Absorbance measurements were made with an ECIL GS-865 spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm matched cuvettes. The pH of the solutions were measured with a Systronic pH meter type 322.

Recommended procedure for the determination of manganese: To a suitable aliquot (1-2 ml) of the solution containing 10-100 μg of the metal, taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask, add 2 ml of the reagent solution. Adjust the pH to 8.4-9.8 with dilute ammonia and allow to stand for 2 min with occasional shaking. Dilute to volume with enough water and ethanol so as to give a final 70% concentration of the latter. Measure the absorbance at 590 nm against alcohol as blank.

Results and Discussion

The instantaneously developed manganese-HPBBAH complex shows an absorption maxima at 590 nm. The reagent has practically no absorbance at 450 nm and above and hence for all photometric measurements alcohol was used as blank. The colour is stable atleast for 2 hr in the temperature range 20-40°. The absorption of the complex remains constant and maximum in the pH range from 8.4 to 9.8. Therefore, a pH value of 9.1 \pm 0.1 was arbitrarily chosen for the spectrophotometric studies. To achieve maximum colour development, a 1 to 80 molar ratio of the metal to reagent is necessary. In practice, for every 100 μg of the metal 40 mg of the reagent was employed. A 1:400 manganese to ligand ratio has been studied to have no adverse effect on the determination. The order of the addition of the reagents is critical.

The system adheres to Beer's law upto 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of manganese concentration. Ringbom's plot¹¹ suggests an effective metal concentration range of 2.0-9.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity of the complex is 5.33×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 590 nm (on the basis of the manganese content). The sensitivity of the colour reaction according to Sandell's definition¹² ($\log I_0/I = 0.001$) is 0.0103 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. Ten independent determinations on solutions each containing 50 μg of Mn(II)/10 ml gave a mean absorbance value of 0.485 and a standard deviation of ± 0.003 or a relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.61\%$. The method is, thus, fairly precise and reproducible.